

SYSTEMATIC ORGANIZATION OF SPIRITUAL AND
EDUCATIONAL WORK IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Annoyance: Conducting conversations and meetings, educational events aimed at forming love and loyalty to the motherland, humane qualities, the role and importance of national customs, traditions and values in our lives in every way; it is one of the priorities of the state policy implemented today.

Keywords: Homeland, state, identity, humanitarianism, virtue, spiritual, national, custom, tradition, value, conversation, meeting, educational event, democratic.

In the reforms in the social sphere carried out in our country, to further strengthen the propaganda work aimed at a specific goal about the spiritual content and essence of the youth, the ancient roots of our national spirituality, unique and unique examples, and the principles of today's development; conducting conversations and meetings, educational events aimed at forming love and loyalty to the Motherland, humane qualities among broad sections of the population, especially young people, and revealing the role and importance of national customs, traditions and values in our lives in every way; it is one of the priorities of the state policy implemented today.

At present, the problem of national identity is becoming a very urgent problem of youth spirituality. Because on the one hand, under the influence of globalization, the earth composed of different nationalities is being integrated into a single cultural world, and on the other hand, preserving national identity is becoming an important factor in preserving the nation. In fact, from the point of

view of today's existence, identity is manifested as a means of explaining the essence of the history and historical trials of the construction of ethnic unity, nation, national statehood.

The idea, purpose, and scope of thoughts of the Decree of the President of our country "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" are of great social importance. The factors of implementation of this decree created a sense of awareness of the high values of modern education in the society. Today's in the day education in front of standing important from issues one is this in youth national spirituality is formation . The educational traditions of our people are important in the formation of spirituality.

The role of educational traditions of our people in the process of formation of national identity in students deserves special attention.

After gaining independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan is on the way to qualitatively renewing all spheres of its life, building a civil society based on a secular democratic state and a market economy. mobilization is required. However, this process does not happen by itself. Society has never been indifferent to how young people are formed.

In the politics of our country, the society's reliance on high spirituality and the formation of an enlightened person has a special place. In solving the first priority task of the third millennium - the formation of a new generation, a great place has been reserved for the strengthening of strong spiritual concepts, humanitarian and democratic values, knowledge of historical roots, and restoration of national traditions in the minds of young people.

Today, the policy of our country is a matter of educating the growing young generation in all aspects. After all, the development of a civil democratic state and the development of our society depends on the level of education and intellectual potential of young people. Conscious attitude towards moral values and civic duty is a multi-faceted process that covers all spheres of social life. A number of legal

documents have been adopted by our government in order to create conditions for young people to grow up healthy and mature.

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Searching for effective forms and methods of raising a highly spiritual person through the systematic organization of spiritual and educational work in educational institutions, developing technology for meaningful organization of free time of students and youth, strengthening cooperation between state and civil society institutions in increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work, educational, spiritual in educational institutions - educational process is crucial. Because the socio-humanitarian, natural and concrete sciences taught in educational institutions, organized spiritual and educational events are an important factor in raising the spirituality of young people.

In his Address to the Oliy Majlis, the President mentioned the following points: "In order to increase the knowledge and level of not only the youth, but also the members of our society, first of all, knowledge and high spirituality are needed. Where there is no knowledge, there will be backwardness, ignorance and, of course, error. As the sages of the East said, "The greatest wealth is intelligence and knowledge, the greatest inheritance is a good upbringing, and the greatest poverty is ignorance."

Therefore, in order to increase the knowledge and thinking of the young generation, it is the most important task of today to inculcate creative ideas in young people in the family, in all types of education, to strengthen their ideological and ideological immunity against foreign ideas, and to protect them from threats on the Internet.

In conclusion, we should emphasize that studying the issues of cooperation between educational institutions and civil society institutions in the formation of youth spirituality is one of the requirements of the currently developing civil society of our country. The goal of establishing a democratic legal state and a strong democratic society in Uzbekistan led to the establishment of human rights and interests as the most priority direction of the development of society and state building. In this regard, our head of state said: "... the large-scale reforms carried out in Uzbekistan today are, first of all, very harmonious and harmonious with the principle of communication with the people, and serve to increase the efficiency of our work."

One of the main tasks of strengthening our independence is to raise the morale of young people, to prepare them to respect universal values , to fulfill the tasks of the national idea, to raise the level of cultural consciousness, to care about the prospects and independence of Uzbekistan, to understand the dignity and honor of themselves and their people, their homeland, and protect it. , is to educate a mature generation who will work in harmony with lofty ideas, new intellectual discoveries, intentions, and give their best to the development of the country and the people.

The spirituality of any people or nation cannot be imagined without its history, customs and traditions, national values. Spiritual heritage, cultural treasures, old historical monuments, folk art are one of the important factors in the formation and development of youth spirituality.

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